

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF USING INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MUSIC TEACHING

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of using innovative and effective pedagogical technologies and its pedagogical aspects in the process of musical education.

Key words: Music education, methodology, innovative technology, pedagogical activity, aspect, culture, Design methodology.

Introduction:

Modernization of education in the modern world constitutes the goals and tasks facing higher education. Today, innovative pedagogical technologies are being introduced, which ensure consideration and development of individual characteristics of musical education students. Modern educational technologies can be considered as the main condition for improving the quality of education, reducing the burden of students, and making effective use of study time.

MATERIALS:

The main goal of modern musical education is "formation of musical culture as an integral part of spiritual culture". Here are some of the current problems of modern music education:

- use of a comprehensive approach to teaching based on the interaction of various art forms;
- introduction of new educational technologies;
- use of modern methods of musical education;
- principles of art didactics;
- use of innovative forms of work.

The purpose of this work: to theoretically justify, present and demonstrate the principles of using innovative pedagogical technologies in music lessons.

Tasks of using innovative pedagogical technologies in music lessons:

1. Defining the concept, methods, and methods of innovative technologies;
2. Analysis of the existing experience in the use of innovative technologies in music lessons;
3. To determine the ways of development of pedagogical activity to fulfill the requirements of the state educational standard.

Innovation is the use of the results of scientific research and development aimed at improving the process of production activity, economic, legal and social relations in science, culture, education and other fields of activity.

The definition of "innovation" as a pedagogic criterion is often found recently and means "innovation" in translation, or rather "new".

Technology is a set of techniques used in any field, craft, art.

Pedagogical technology is a thought-out model of joint pedagogical activity in all details of designing, organizing and implementing the educational process with unconditional provision of comfortable conditions for teachers and students.

METHODS:

Innovative technologies - an algorithm of sequential actions aimed at obtaining a positive final result in an interdependent system, alternative technologies related to changes in the organizational forms of the educational process.

Innovative technologies include:

1. Creating a scheme of cognitive thinking;
2. Cultivate self-esteem;
3. Differential approach;
4. Good knowledge of theoretical material;
5. Creating a problematic situation;
6. Working with gifted children.

Innovative technologies include:

1. Increase the level of motivation for studying;
2. Formation of high-level development of students based on participation in activities that are constantly becoming more complex;
3. Creating a friendly atmosphere, creating a positive attitude to learning through individual treatment for each student.

Innovative technologies in music lessons help to form the skills of active perception of music, enrich children's musical experience, absorb knowledge, achieve success and, through sensory, emotional experiences and feelings, improve the spirituality, culture, consciousness, and moral status of students to a certain extent. helps to raise.

Innovative processes in the field of musical education are always creativity, it is always a discovery, the birth of something new. It is in music lessons that it is possible to create the most favorable environment for the all-round development of a child, to reveal the potential of his creative abilities and the prospects of his future career.

The use of innovative pedagogical technologies is impossible without familiarization with innovative musical and pedagogical experience, systems and technologies of teaching science and includes knowledge of the main directions and perspectives of the development of pedagogical science. The availability of educational programs and textbooks, the use of educational tools and their didactic capabilities, the ability to use modern scientifically based methods, methods and tools of music education, including technical, information and computer technologies.

A modern music lesson is a lesson that uses modern pedagogical technologies, computer technologies, and electronic musical instruments. The music lesson is characterized by creating a creative environment, the content of these lessons consists of emotions and their subjective experience. Such content determines the choice of different methods, types of work and new multimedia tools.

The use of innovative technologies makes it possible to implement the plan and make the lesson modern. The use of computer technologies in the educational process affects the growth of the teacher's professional skills, which helps to significantly improve the quality of education.

An important basis for understanding the innovations of modern music and educational theory and practice is the methodology of music education.

Information and communication technologies in music education.

Information and communication technologies are a very necessary tool in music lessons. The use of multimedia tools is the development of the innovative thinking of the child during the study of artistic and aesthetic subjects in educational institutions, the optimization of their intellectual development and the educational process, and the development of the creative competence of students.

Today, there are a variety of electronic publications that can be used in music and educational activities. "*Encyclopedia of classical music*" contains 278 articles about composers of all countries, 209 pieces of music of the most famous works and descriptions of their content. The animation shows 44 musical instruments and their sound samples. Over a hundred articles introduce you to the most famous performers from around the world. The authors describe ten main genres of music (opera, ballet, operetta, symphony, concerto, sonata, piano music, chamber music, cantatas and oratorios, and romances) with illustrations, video fragments, and musical sound fragments.

Information and communication technologies allow students to prepare an interesting presentation instead of boring abstracts. When working on the presentation, the student should conduct extensive scientific research, use a large number of sources of information that will allow turning each work into a product of individual creativity. When creating each slide in the presentation, the student becomes a computer creator (*the slide should be aesthetic and reflect the author's inner attitude to the presented issue*). This type of educational activity allows students to develop creative thinking and develop skills. During the presentation process, students will gain experience in public speaking, which will definitely be useful in their later life.

Design methodology.

The use of students' project activities in music lessons helps to attract students to the topic - regulation, science - cognitive and communicative activities, thereby contributing to the formation of communicative competence, increasing students' interest in learning. Each project must require student research. A characteristic feature of the project activity is the search for information that is later processed, understood and presented by the members of the project team.

The school project has the following structure:

1. Preparation including the following steps:

- project planning by the teacher within the program topics;
- presentation of the idea by the teacher in the lesson;
- discussion of the idea by students;
- promotion of their ideas by them;
- argue their points.

2. Work organization:

- formation of micro groups;
- determining the goals and tasks of the project, formulating problematic issues;
- distribution of tasks in micro groups;
- practical activities of students within the project.

3. The final stage:

- interim control (with a long-term project);
- discuss the project design method;
- formalization of the project;
- presentation of project results;
- project completion: discussion of results, evaluation, etc.

4. Stage of practical use of project results.

In the defense of the project, students use information and communication technologies, which makes the lesson informative, diverse and, most importantly, modern. Creating conditions for design and research work in the lesson helps to actively involve students in creative research, increases the amount of independently acquired knowledge. The project always gives the student an opportunity for self-study.

Results:

After studying the concept of innovative technologies, getting acquainted with the experience of using them in music lessons, I came to the opinion that it is necessary to use various innovative technologies in music lessons in the context of the implementation of pedagogical technologies. All these technologies make it possible to achieve the main goal: development of intellectual, moral, creative development of a person, education of artistic culture of students.

The experience of leading teachers has shown that it is not possible to rely only on the content of the studied material to develop interest in the subject. If the students are not actively participating, then any material will arouse their interest in the topic.

Conclusion:

In my further pedagogical work, I consider it necessary to use and introduce innovative pedagogical technologies, because they meet all modern requirements of education, music lessons are interesting, bright, cognitive, and allow to form universal educational activities, which in turn, it helps to form meta-science results that meet the principles of work according to the State educational standard.

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